

Tailoring the Shape Memory Properties of Segmented Poly(ester urethanes) via Blending

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Abstract: Thermoplastic segmented polyurethanes (PUs) can exhibit shape memory (SM) behavior, if they feature multiple kinds of physical cross-links that can be dissociated at different temperatures. This is the case if the hydrogen-bonded hard phase is joined with soft segments that can partially crystallize, so that the melting transition acts as the memory switch. For applications in the biomedical field, it is important that the fixation and recovery temperatures can be minutely controlled. We show here that this tailoring can be easily achieved by formulating a commercial PU featuring poly(1,4-butylene adipate) (PBA) as a crystallizable segment (PBA-PU) with either PBA or poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL) of moderate molecular weight. We show that the nature of the end groups and the processing conditions dictate if there is any reaction between the components, or if the product is merely a blend. Interestingly, in either case, the addition of PBA or PCL causes nucleation and thereby a noteworthy increase of the crystallization temperature of the switching element from below to above ambient temperature, so that excellent shape fixity ($\sim 98\%$) can be achieved at $37\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The melting temperature is maintained above 50°C and significant increases in strength and modulus are achieved. The new materials platform is well suited for applications in which a shape is to be fixed at physiological temperature.

Keywords: Shape memory polymer, poly(ester urethane), melt-mixing, blends, nucleation, shape fixation

Introduction

Shape memory polymers (SMPs) can be transformed into a temporary shape by subjecting them simultaneously to a mechanical force and another stimulus such as heat, light, an electromagnetic field, or a pH change, and can later assume their original or permanent shape upon exposure to the same or another stimulus.¹⁻⁷ SMPs require a structure that provides rubber elasticity and a switching phase that is responsive to an external stimulus and serves as a second type of cross-link that can be switched on or off. Heat^{1, 8-10} is the most common stimulus used to control shape memory effects in polymers, but the introduction of light-active¹¹⁻¹², pH active¹³, or water active¹⁴ moieties into elastic polymer networks enables activation by other stimuli. Many different SMPs have been investigated for potential use in advanced technological and biomedical applications.^{4-6, 15-16} Continuous efforts have been dedicated to the overall improvement of the SMPs, although aspects such as limited stiffness,¹⁷⁻¹⁹ low recovery stress,²⁰ long response time,²¹ or limited durability of the SM behavior²²⁻²³ restrict their potential technological use. While the properties of SMPs can *a priori* be tailored through the variation of their composition, a given material can also be modified by fabricating (nano)composites²⁴⁻²⁵ by adding micro- or nanometer sized fillers such as fibers,²⁶⁻²⁷ particles,²⁸⁻²⁹ or nanocrystals.³⁰⁻³¹ A related design approach to either create new shape memory polymers or modifying the properties of existing SMPs is the fabrication of blends. For example, SMPs can be created by combining an elastic polymer with a second polymer that forms the fixing phase,^{32,33} such as a semicrystalline or amorphous polymer whose mechanical properties can be switched by heating above the melting (T_m) or glass transition (T_g) temperature.³⁶⁻³⁸ Further, binary blends of two crystalline polymers, in which one crystal type forms the fixing phase and the other a reversible cross-linking phase, also display shape-memory behavior.³⁴⁻³⁵ The properties of existing SMPs

can also be modified by blending them with another polymer, which may have the same or a different chemical structure as the segments of which the SMP is comprised.³³ For instance, shape memory polymer blends of a PU with a phenoxy resin or poly(vinyl chloride) were reported, which exhibited tunable switching transition temperature and improved mechanical properties, respectively.³⁹⁻⁴⁰

Especially for biomedical applications, it is important that the fixation and recovery temperatures can be minutely tailored around the human body temperature.⁴¹⁻⁴² It can further be advantageous if the mechanical characteristics of a given materials platform can be modified without *de novo* synthesis of the SMP. In this context, we recently reported the modification of a commercial shape-memory polyurethane⁴³⁻⁴⁶ featuring hard segments obtained by reacting of 4,4'-methylene-diphenyl diisocyanate (MDI) with 1,4-butanediol (PBA-PU)⁴⁷⁻⁴⁹ and crystallizable poly(1,4-butylene adipate) (PBA) soft blocks that acts as the switching segments. We formulated nanocomposites with cellulose nanocrystals and influenced the crystallization behavior of the PBA segments by incorporating a nucleating agent.⁵⁰ We demonstrated that the fixing temperature could be raised from 10 to 25 °C by the adding a small amount of dodecanoic acid, which reacts with the PBA, reduces the molecular weight, and has a nucleating effect.⁵⁰ We show here that the fixing temperature can be further increased by melt-mixing PBA-PU with free PBA or poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL). Indeed, it was possible to achieve excellent shape fixity (~98%) at physiological temperature (37 °C). This is important as there are many examples of SMPs designed for biomedical applications that are applied in a temporary shape with the goal to restore the permanent shape inside or around the body, using a suitable trigger. Conversely, in the present study we present materials that allow an inversion of this scheme. The new materials become shapeable above a switching temperature of ca. 50 °C and remain shapeable when cooled

to physiological temperature so that they can be programmed to assume a desired temporary shape at body temperature, which is fixed at this temperature in a convenient period of time.

Experimental Section

Materials. The PBA-PU used was received from Covestro Deutschland AG under the designation Desmopan DP 2795 A. Dihydroxy-terminated poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL) (weight-average molecular weight, $M_w = 14,000 \text{ g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$) and poly(1,4-butylene adipate) (PBA) ($M_w = 12,000 \text{ g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$) were acquired from Sigma Aldrich.

Synthesis of AcPBA. The end-capped AcPBA was prepared by acetylation of PBA with acetyl chloride in THF/pyridine. PBA (4.0 g, 0.33 mmol) was dissolved in dry THF (20 mL), pyridine (0.270 mL, 3.3 mmol) was added, and the mixture was cooled in an ice bath. Under stirring at 0 °C acetyl chloride (0.235 mL, 3.3 mmol) was dropwise added, causing a white precipitate to form. After the addition was complete, the ice bath was removed and the mixture was stirred for another 2 h at RT. The mixture was then poured into ice-cold water and the white solid was collected by filtration, washed with an abundant amount of water, methanol and finally dried under vacuum. AcPBA was isolated in quantitative yield as a white solid. ^1H NMR (chloroform- d , 400 MHz): δ 4.08 (t, 4H, CH_2O), 2.31 (t, 4H, CH_2CO), 2.04 (s, end group, CH_3CO), 1.68 (m, 8H, CH_2), 1.64 (m, 8H, CH_2). FT-IR (ATR, cm^{-1}): 582, 585, 734, 911, 930, 958 1066, 1141, 1162, 1257, 1317, 1333, 1369, 1401, 1504, 1508, 1540, 1723 2956.

Fabrication of Blends of PBA-PU with PBA, AcPBA, or PCL. The PBA-PU was dried for 3 h at 70 °C prior to the fabrication of the blends. PBA-PU was blended with 10, 20, or 30% w/w of PBA by processing the two components at a temperature of 180 °C and a mixing speed of 70 rpm in a type 30EHT roller blade mixer (RBM, Brabender® GmbH & Co. KG). This was

accomplished by first introducing the PBA-PU into the mixing device, and operating the RBM until the polymer was thoroughly melted (6 min). The PBA was then added to the PU melt and for another 4 min both components were mixed together. The combined weight of the two components was kept constant at 20 g. After the mixing was complete, the materials were removed from the RBM device and cooled to ambient. All materials were compression-molded into 300 μm thin films in a Carver® press between poly(tetrafluoroethylene) (PTFE) sheets at 180 °C under a pressure of 4 metric tons for 5 min. The films were then removed from the press and between the PTFE sheets to ambient. PBA-PU reference films were made using the same protocol of processing the polymer in the RBM and subsequent compression molding. A 20% w/w PBA-PU/AcPBA blend and a 30% w/w PBA-PU/PCL blend were produced using the same protocol, but in the case of the PBA-PU/AcPBA blend, the processing temperature was increased to 190 °C. All samples were stored under ambient conditions in a desiccator for 48 h before analysis. Solution-cast films of the 20% w/w PBA-PU/PBA blend were prepared by dissolving the PBA-PU (0.80 g) and PBA (0.20 g) in warm THF (40 mL), casting the solution into a PTFE Petri dish, and drying at ambient temperature over a period of 3 days. A portion of the solution-cast material was re-shaped by compression-molding as described above. Irrespective of the actual structure, the compositions reported here are, for convenience, referred to as “compositions”, “blends”, or “mixtures”.

Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) Spectroscopy. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Avance III HD spectrometer at 400 MHz (1H). Referencing was done with solvent protons, but chemical shifts (δ) are expressed in ppm (parts per million), relative to tetramethylsilane.

Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy. FT-IR spectra were measured on a Spectrum 65 spectrometer from PerkinElmer in attenuated total reflection mode.

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC). DSC experiments were conducted with a Mettler-Toledo STAR system under N₂, with sample amounts of ~8 mg, heating and cooling rates of 10 °C·min⁻¹, and unless otherwise noted between 0 and 100 °C. The maxima of the melting endotherm and the cooling exotherm were taken as the melting (T_m) and crystallization temperature (T_c) and are reported in **Table 1**.

Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA). Thermogravimetric analyses were carried out using a Mettler-Toledo STAR thermogravimetric analyzer under N₂ atmosphere, with sample amounts of ~5 mg, a heating rate of 10 °C·min⁻¹ and unless otherwise noted between 25 and 600 °C.

Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA). The dynamic mechanical testing was done on a TA Instrument DMA Q800 in tensile mode, at a frequency of 1 Hz, a strain amplitude of 15 μm, and unless otherwise noted with a heating rate of 5 °C·min⁻¹ between -50 and 200 °C. For these experiments, films were cut in the form of 5-6 mm wide and 8 mm long strips. Stress-strain experiments were performed with the same instrument at 25 °C and a strain rate of 5%·min⁻¹ using dog-bone shaped samples. DMA results reported are averages of 3–5 independent measurements ± standard deviation.

Size Exclusion Chromatography. An Agilent Technologies 1260 Infinity was used to conduct size exclusion chromatography (SEC). A refractive index detector was used in connection with one guard column, two 10 μm linear mixed-bed PSS GRAM columns (300 mm × 8.0 mm), and the system was operated at 55 °C. The mobile phase was DMF with 0.05 M LiBr 0.05M and a flow rate of 0.5 mL·min⁻¹ was used. Poly(methyl methacrylate) standards were used for calibration and processing was done using the PSS WinGPC Unchrom.

Optical Microscopy. An Olympus BX51 microscope fitted with a DP72 digital camera and a Linkam LTS350 heating/cooling stage was used. All images were acquired at 50x magnification.

Small and Wide-Angle X-Ray Scattering. Films of the neat PBA (compression molded at 80 °C, under 3 metric tons pressure for 5 min), the PBA-PU, and its blends with 10 or 20% w/w PBA were analyzed by small-angle and wide-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS, WAXS). The measurements were carried out using a NanoMax-IQ camera (Rigaku Innovative Technologies), a Pilatus100 K detector (Dectris), and using a Cu target sealed tube source (MicroMax-003, Rigaku) in vacuum and at ambient temperature. The acquired data were processed using routine protocols. The scattering intensity is shown as a function of the momentum transfer $q = 4\pi\lambda^{-1} \sin(\theta/2)$, where λ is the photon wavelength of 0.1524 nm and θ is the scattering angle. Selected spectra were fitted in the range of 14.5-16 nm⁻¹ against a linear combination of Gaussian functions (interpreting the Bragg-reflections from the crystal planes) and a quadratic function (interpreting the amorphous halo).

Shape Memory Analysis. A TA Instrument DMA Q800 was used in controlled-force mode to conduct repeated stress-temperature-strain tests. The samples were first heated to 70 °C, maintained at this temperature for 5 min, before the force was increased at a rate of 0.8 N·min⁻¹ up to 18 N to cause uniaxial sample deformation. Upon reaching a strain limit of 40% the stress and temperature (70 °C) were maintained for 5 min, before the temperature was dropped to 0 (PBA-PU), 10 (PBA-PU), 20 or 25°C (blends of PBA-PU with 10, 20% w/w PBA), 30 or 37 °C (20 and 30% w/w PBA-PU/PBA, 30% w/w PBA-PU/PCL and 20% w/w PBA-PU/AcPBA) at a rate of 5 °C·min⁻¹. The samples were kept strained at the respective fixing temperature for 5 min, 15 min (samples fixed at 25, 30 or 37 °C only), 20 min (30% w/w PBA-PU/PBA fixed at 37 °C)

or 30 min (20% w/w PBA-PU/PBA, 20 % w/w PBA-PU/AcPBA and 30% w/w PBA-PU/PCL fixed at 37 °C), changes in strain were recorded and the force was released. After a pause of 5 min, the cycle was closed by heating to 70 °C at a rate of 5 °C·min⁻¹, and keeping the samples at 70 °C for 10 min. Unless otherwise noted, 3 cycles were applied. The values of the fixity (%) and recovery (%) reported in **Table 3** calculated for each cycle according to Eqs. (1) and (2):

$$\% \text{ Fixity} = \frac{\epsilon_u - \epsilon_i}{\epsilon_s - \epsilon_i} \times 100 \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

$$\% \text{ Recovery} = \frac{\epsilon_u - \epsilon_r}{\epsilon_u - \epsilon_i} \times 100 \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

where ϵ_i is the initial strain, and ϵ_s , ϵ_u , and ϵ_r are the strains after deformation, unloading, and recovery, respectively.

An alternative shape memory cycle was also used to investigate the behavior when deforming the materials only after first cooling them to the fixing temperature. As for the shape memory test described above, the cyclic tests start with heating the sample to 70 °C and keeping them at 70 °C for 5 min. The samples were then cooled to 37 °C (rate 5 °C/min) to simulate the deployment of an object or a device, and kept at this temperature for 2 min, before they were uniaxially deformed, as described above, and kept under load isothermally for 15 min. Subsequently, the stress was removed and the cycle was continued as described above.

Results and Discussion

The poly(urethane) employed here, PBA-PU, is commercially available and features a hard phase that is formed by the reaction of 4,4'-methylenebis(phenyl isocyanate) and 1,4-butanediol and a soft phase based on poly(1,4-butylene adipate), which partially crystallizes upon cooling to

sub-ambient temperature and can thus be utilized to fix and release a temporary shape. Likely on account of the reduced mobility, the melting and crystallization temperatures of the PBA segments in PBA-PU are both about 20°C lower than the corresponding transitions in neat PBA of moderate molecular weight (**Figure 1 a,b**). Speculating that the addition of free PBA could have a nucleating effect, PBA-PU was blended with 10 - 30% w/w PBA by melt-mixing the components at 180 °C. The resulting materials were compression molded at the same temperature into 300 µm thin films, cooled to room temperature, and stored for two days at room temperature before any experiments were conducted.

The thermal behavior of the various PBA-PU/PBA mixtures was investigated by thermogravimetric analyses (TGA) and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) experiments. TGA measurements under nitrogen reveal that PBA-PU and its blends with PBA display only a moderate weight loss (around 5%) upon heating to above 300 °C (**Figure S1**). The thermal transitions of all materials were analyzed by DSC experiments. Previous studies have established that the neat PBA⁵¹ as well as the PBA phase of PBA-PU⁴⁷ display a rather complicated crystallization behavior. Crystallization at different temperatures leads to different ratios of two polymorphs, the thermodynamically preferred α and the kinetically favored β form. Recrystallization from the β to the higher melting α form is possible, and the latter, due to variations in crystal size, is responsible for two distinct melting transitions. Thus, a broad melting range with more or less well resolved peaks is usually observed. **Figure 1a** and **b** show the first heating and cooling traces of the neat PBA-PU and its blends with PBA; the melting (T_m) and crystallization (T_c) temperatures extracted from these measurements are compiled in **Table 1**. In the first heating of the neat PBA-PU a broad melting peak centered around 47°C and a shoulder at 52 °C is observed. The pattern is consistent with an initial combination of α and β crystals,

recrystallization of the β into the α polymorph, and melting of recrystallized α crystals.^{47, 52-53} Upon cooling, the neat PBA-PU shows a crystallization peak that sets in at around 15 °C and has a maximum at 7 °C. The first DSC heating trace of the neat PBA shows a more narrow melting peak with an onset at 55 °C and a maximum at 62 °C, while the second heating trace shows two transitions at 48 and 55 °C, characteristic of a mixture of β and high temperature melting α form (**Figure S2**). The cooling curve of the neat PBA shows an onset of the crystallization at 35 °C and a maximum around 28 °C (**Figure 1b**), while the second cooling curve shows maximum at 32 °C (**Figure S2**).

The first heating traces of the PBA-PU/PBA blends with 10, 20 or 30% w/w PBA exhibit a broad melting transition with multiple peaks in the 35-55 °C range and maxima at 52-53 °C, indicative of a mixture of α and β forms; interestingly, in the case of the 20 and 30% w/w PBA-PU/PBA blend, the DSC trace suggests a majority of (smaller) α crystals (**Figure 1a, Table 1**). Note the absence of the melting peak associated with the neat PBA at a slightly higher temperature. The cooling scans of the PBA-PU/PBA blends each show only one peak, with a maximum at 18, 23 or 29 °C for 10, 20 and 30% w/w PBA-PU/PBA blends, respectively (**Figure 1b, Table 1**). Taken together, the results show that the addition of PBA has a pronounced nucleating effect on the PBA segments that are covalently incorporated in the PBA-PU. We show later that (a portion) of the added PBA reacts with the PBA-PU, either through trans-esterification or an opening of the urea bonds, leading to either longer PBA chains in this polymer or PBA chain ends, both of which also can serve to nucleate the crystallization of the material (*vide infra*). Similar observations were noted in a previous study of PCL-PU/PCL blends, wherein the size of PCL crystals was shown to decrease with increasing PU content.⁵³⁻⁵⁴ However, the former study targeted a reduction of the PCL melting and crystallization temperature through the addition of

amorphous PCL-PU, as a result of the reduced segmental mobility of PCL, its dilution in the blend, and the decrease in super-cooling due to the reduced melting temperature.

Figure 1. Graphs showing the first heating (a,c) and the first cooling DSC traces (b, d) of PBA-PU and its blends with PBA (a,b) or PCL (c,d). Traces of the neat PBA and PCL are also included. The numbers indicate the maxima of the melting/crystallization peaks. The inset in (d) shows a magnification of the peaks seen in the 30% w/w PBA-PU/PCL mixture. The heating/cooling rates in all experiments were 10 °C/min.

To demonstrate broader applicability of the approach, we also investigated a melt-mixed blend of PBA-PU and 10, 20 or 30% w/w PCL. Gratifyingly, the DSC data reflect a behavior that is similar to that of the PBA-PU/PBA blends. With increasing PCL content the melting transition sharpened (**Figure 1c**) and T_m increased to 54°C. The heating traces are void of the signal around 69 °C, where the neat PCL melts (**Figure 1c, Table 1**). The first cooling cycles show that the T_c

also increased upon addition of PCL from 7 to 25 °C and as for the blends with PBA T_c depends on the amount of polymer added (**Figure 1d**). Only the DSC trace of the 30% w/w PBA-PU/PCL mixture shows a faint shoulder around 34 °C (**Figure 1d, Table 1**), which appears to be associated with PCL crystallization) and indicates the formation of a discrete PCL phase at this concentration. The fact that in all three PCL blends the crystallization of the PBA crystals is shifted to a temperature higher than that of neat PBA-PU, while the melting transition reflects the formation of the PBA α form, suggests that also the addition of PCL also nucleates the crystallization of the PBA-PU.

Table 1. Melting and crystallization temperatures (T_m , T_c) of PBA-PU, PBA, PCL, and the blends studied.^a

Composition	PBA/PCL Content (w/w)	T_m (°C)	T_c (°C)
PBA	0%	62	28
PCL	0%	69	26
PBA-PU	0%	56	6
PBA-PU/PBA	10%	53	18
	20%	52	23
	30%	54	29
PBA-PU/PCL	10%	53	11
	20%	53	17
	30%	54	25

^aDetermined by DSC. The heating and cooling rates were 10 °C/min.

Isothermal DSC studies were undertaken to test the possibility to crystallize the PBA-PU/PBA blends above the T_c established by DSC and in particular at physiological temperature. Although the crystallization onset measured by DSC for all PBA-PU/ blends studied is below 37 °C

(**Figure 2**), crystallization is possible when T is $T_c \geq T > T_m$ and the rate increases as T approaches T_c . To investigate this samples were placed in the DSC, heated to 100 °C, maintained at this temperature for 5 min and then rapidly (cooling rate -40 °C/min) cooled to 37 °C. The heat flow at 37 °C was recorded for 50 min (**Figure 2a**) and the traces clearly show that, while for the neat PBA-PU no exothermic process takes place within the timeframe of the experiment, for the 10% composition a very broad (i.e. slow) crystallization process is recorded, which is further accelerated for the 20 and 30% compositions. The traces indicate that the crystallization of the PBA segments is largely complete after 20 and 10 min for the 20 and 30% w/w blends, respectively. After the isothermal DSC experiments were completed, the samples were further heated from 37 °C up to 100 °C in order to detect the melting of the crystalline domains formed during annealing at 37 °C (**Figure 2b**). As expected, no endothermic process was observed for the neat PBA-PU, confirming the inability of the neat poly(ester urethane) to crystallize at 37 °C within a desirable timeframe. Conversely, melting peaks are recorded for the PBA-PU/PBA blends with enthalpies increasing with increasing PBA content, clearly confirming that isothermal crystallization at 37 °C is possible in the case of the PBA-PU/PBA blends.

Figure 2. (a) Isothermal DSC traces of PBA-PU and the PBA-PU/PBA mixtures with 10, 20, 30% w/w PBA at 37 °C; the traces were recorded after first heating the samples to 100 °C and cooling to 37 °C; and (b) subsequent heating traces (recorded after the traces shown in (a) were recorded) from 37 °C to 100 °C (heating rate 10 °C/min).

The morphology of PBA-PU and its blends with PBA was probed by polarized optical microscopy under dynamic heating and cooling. A comparison between neat PBA-PU and the 20% w/w PBA-PU/PBA mixture was obtained by placing the two films (one 0.2 mm thick film per composition) side-by-side on a glass slide. The samples were first heated from 25 °C to 70 °C and maintained at 70 °C for 10 min. Images taken with the samples between crossed polarizers show the loss of birefringence for both samples, on account of melting of the PBA crystals (**Figure 3a**). Next, the samples were cooled to 37 °C and kept at this temperature for 50 min. Cross-polarized micrographs taken at regular time intervals visibly show the rapid formation (10-15 min) of PBA crystallites in the 20% w/w PBA-PU/PBA sample (**Figure 3b**, left side of every picture), whereas no crystallization is visible for the neat PBA-PU (**Figure 3b**, right side of every picture).

Figure 3. Polarized optical microscopy images showing a side-by-side comparison of the temperature induced morphological changes in PBA-PU and PBA-PU/PBA 20% blend during heating (a) and cooling isothermally at 37 °C (b) for the neat PBA-PU (right side in each picture) and the 20% w/w PBA-PU/PBA blend (left side). The scale bar on the pictures is 100 μm .

Figure 4 shows the wide-angle X-ray scattering (WAXS) patterns of the neat PBA-PU, PBA, and the PBA-PU blends with 10, 20, or 30% w/w PBA. The spectrum of the neat PBA shows four characteristic peaks with q -values at 14.95, 15.18, 15.69, and 17.14 nm⁻¹ (**Figure 4, Figure S3a**), corresponding to a mixture of α and β crystal forms, which is in agreement with a previous report.⁵¹ The WAXS spectrum of PBA-PU shows a similar spectrum (**Figure 4**) and the peak center positions are virtually the same (**Figure S3b**); however, the distribution of the scattering intensities is shifted and suggests a higher fraction of β than α crystals. The scattering pattern of the 10% w/w PBA-PU/PBA blend is nearly the same as that of the neat PBA-PU (**Figure 4, Figure S3c**), whereas those of the 20 and 30% w/w PBA/PBA-PU blends shows a peak pattern that is void of the peaks associated with β crystals (**Figure 4**). The WAXS spectrum confirms the presence of only α peaks (**Figure S3d, e**). This suggests that in the 20 and 30% w/w PBA-PU/PBA blend, the PU bound PBA and the free PBA may co-crystallize to form thermodynamically stable α crystallites,⁵² on account of the increased content of PBA and the slower crystal growth rate owing to the mobility limiting effect imparted by the PU network. Thus, quite surprisingly, the incorporation of free PBA into the PBA-PU not only leads to an increase of the crystallization temperature, but can also have a significant influence on the crystal structure. The SAXS spectra of the neat PBA-PU, the PBA, and the PBA-PU/PBA blends support the conclusion drawn; the diffraction patterns are consistent with the formation of two phases formed by the PU's hard segments and the PBA, respectively, but no formation of a discrete phase formed by the added PBA can be discerned (**Figure S4**). Interestingly, SAXS spectra also support the absence of a third phase in the 10 and 20% w/w PBA-PU/PCL blends (**Figure S4**), whereas SAXS and WAXS (**Figure S4**) spectra of the 30% w/w PBA-PU/PCL blend indeed show the presence of a discrete PCL phase, as also suggested by the DSC data (**Figure 1d**).

Figure 4. WAXS spectra of PBA, PBA-PU, and PBA-PU/PBA blends. The spectra are vertically shifted for clarity.

A comparison of the size exclusion chromatography (SEC) traces of the neat PBA-PU, the neat PBA, and the PBA-PU/PBA blends reveals that the molecular weight of the blends is considerably lower than that of the neat PBA-PU (**Figure 5**). The SEC trace for the 10% w/w PBA-PU/PBA blend shows a single peak, whereas no other peaks, notably those corresponding to either the neat PBA-PU or the free PBA, can be observed. This is indicative of a largely complete reaction between the PBA-PU and the PBA, either by way of transesterification involving the PBA's hydroxyl end groups, or their corresponding reaction with the PBA-PU's urea groups. The 10% w/w PBA-PU/PBA blend thus is not a physical mixture or blend, but rather a new polymer that is characterized by M_n , M_w and D values of 55,900 g/mol, 103,700 g/mol, and 1.8 respectively. The SEC traces of the 20 and the 30% w/w PBA-PU/PBA blends show a main peak that is similar to that of the 10% w/w PBA-PU/PBA blend, although the retention times are slightly higher (indicating lower molecular weights); in addition, a shoulder at higher retention time was observed, which is more prominent in the 30% w/w PBA-PU/PBA blend and likely due to the presence of unreacted or "free" PBA. Note that the reduction in molecular weight is not affecting significantly the mechanical properties of the material (*vide infra*).

The SEC data of the PBA-PU/PCL blends (**Figure S5**) reveal the same behavior, although the extent of molecular weight reduction was less pronounced than in the PBA-PU/PBA blends.

Figure 5. Size-exclusion chromatography traces of the neat PBA-PU, neat PBA, and three PBA-PU/PBA blends containing 10, 20 and 30% w/w PBA. The determined M_n , M_w and \bar{D} are: 110,000 g/mol, 229,000 g/mol and 2.08 for the neat PBA-PU; 55,900 g/mol, 103,700 g/mol and 1.8 for the 10% w/w PBA-PU/PBA; 5,000 g/mol, 9,700 g/mol and 1.9 for the PBA. Given the broadness of the peaks and the vicinity to the injection peak, deconvolution of the two peaks for 20% and 30% w/w PBA-PU/PBA gave no reliable results, overestimating substantially the molecular weight associated with the main peak.

These results raise the question whether the desirable thermal properties of the PBA-PU/PBA blends arise from the increase of the PBA content, the presence of free PBA, or if reaction products, which are thought to feature PBA chain ends, could possibly be responsible for the nucleation. In order to explore this question further, we first prepared a 20% w/w PBA-PU/PBA blend film by solution casting under conditions where any reaction between the components was avoided. The sample was prepared by dissolving the two components in tetrahydrofuran, casting into a mould, and drying at ambient temperature. The DSC analysis of the solvent-cast film (**Figure S6a,b**) reveals a thermal behavior that is very similar to the one of the corresponding melt-mixed material, featuring a melting peak at 56 °C upon heating and a crystallization peak at 20 °C, *ca.* 3 degrees lower than the melt-mixed 20% w/w PBA-PU/PBA blend (*i.e.* 23 °C). The

solvent-cast film was re-processed by compression molding at 180 °C for 3 min, and the T_c of the material increased to 22 °C. Indeed, size exclusion chromatography analyses of the solvent-cast film and the re-molded sample show that, while for the former two distinct peaks corresponding to PBA-PU and PBA are observed, in the case of the latter the brief thermal treatment was found to cause a shift toward lower molecular weights (**Figure S6c**).

Speculating that hydroxyl end groups present in the PBA might be responsible for the reaction and consequent molecular weight reduction during melt mixing with PBA-PU, the PBA was reacted with acetyl chloride in THF/pyridine, which afforded PBA end-capped with acetate groups (AcPBA) in quantitative yield, as confirmed by ^1H NMR and FTIR spectroscopy (**Figure S7**). A 20% w/w PBA-PU/AcPBA blend was then prepared by melt-mixing, assuming that the end capping of PBA should lead to a reduction or suppression of the reaction with the PBA-PU. Indeed, size exclusion chromatography analyses reveal that the 20% w/w melt-mixed PBA-PU/AcPBA blend shows two discrete peaks that overlap with those of the neat PBA-PU (which, for purpose of comparison was also processed in the melt-mixer under identical conditions) and the neat AcPBA, indicating the absence of any significant reaction between PBA-PU and AcPBA (**Figure S8a**). The DSC traces reveal a thermal behavior that is indeed very similar to the one of the corresponding solution cast or melt-mixed materials, featuring a melting peak at 52-53 °C upon heating and a crystallization peak at 23 °C (**Figure S8b**). The isothermal DSC experiment at 37 °C is identical to that of the solution-cast film, whereas the crystallization is slightly slower than in the case of the melt-processed 20% w/w PBA-PU/PBA blend (**Figure S8c**). Finally, the SAXS and WAXS spectra of the 20% w/w PBA-PU/AcPBA are similar to those of the corresponding PBA-PU/PBA blend (**Figure S4**). Thus based on the findings that (a) the 10% w/w melt-processed PBA-PU/PBA blend, which appears to be void of free PBA but has

a reduced molecular weight relative to the neat PBA-PU, (b) the 30% w/w melt-processed PBA-PU/PBA blend, which appears to contain residual free PBA, (c) the solution-cast 20% w/w PBA-PU/PBA and the melt-processed 20% w/w PBA-PU/AcPBA blends, which featured free PBA or AcPBA and shows no significant molecular weight reduction relative to the PBA-PU, all show an increase of T_c , which seems to scale with the PBA content, we conclude that it is primarily the increase of the PBA content that drives the crystallization behavior, although it is also well possible that the effect is connected to an increased mobility of the PBA in the “blends” *vis-à-vis* the original PBA-PU, either because the PBA added remains free, is (through reaction) placed at chain ends, or has a higher molecular weight than the PBA originally present in the PBA-PU. It is further demonstrated that melt mixing, solvent-based methods as well as the use of an unreactive PBA can be employed to prepare shape memory materials and that the molecular weight can be retained or reduced at will.

The mechanical properties of the films of the neat PBA-PU and its blends with 10, 20 or 30% w/w PBA were investigated by dynamic mechanical analyses (DMA). In the case of the neat PBA-PU the graph shows a gradual reduction of the storage modulus (E') upon heating from -50 °C, a sharp, step-like modulus drop around 45-50 °C that is related to the melting of crystalline PBA domains, a rubbery plateau that extends from about 70 to 170 °C, and another sharp modulus reduction above this temperature, which is related to the dissociation of the PU's hard segments (**Figure 6a**). At 25 °C, the blends of PBA-PU with PBA (**Figure 6a**) display an increased storage modulus *vis à vis* the neat PBA-PU (150 MPa); the 10% w/w PBA blend exhibits an E' of 403 MPa, whereas a further increase of the PBA content to 20 and 30% w/w did not change E' much further (412 MPa) (**Table 2**). The shape of the DMA trace remains largely unaffected, although the transition associated with the PBA melting seems to become sharper

upon introduction of the PBA and the temperature at which the hard phase dissociates decreases with increasing PBA content from *ca.* 170 to *ca.* 125 °C for compositions up to 20% w/w and *ca.* 75 °C for the 30% w/w blend. Interestingly, in the rubbery plateau (above the T_m of the PBA) the E' values of the blends are lower than those of the neat polymers, which can be advantageous as the materials are softer and shaping of a temporary shape is easier.

Figure 6. Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) traces (a) and stress-strain curves (b) of the neat PBA-PU and its blends with 10, 20, or 30% PBA.

Figure 6b shows the stress-strain curves of PBA-PU and its blends with PBA, all acquired at 25 °C. The trace of the neat PBA-PU reveals an elastic regime with a Young's modulus of 75 MPa before yielding at a stress and strain of *ca.* 6.7 MPa and 20%, respectively. The plastic regime shows PBA significant strain hardening and the samples fail at a maximum stress of 30 MPa and an elongation of 360% (**Table 2**). This mechanical behavior is consistent with the morphology of the neat PBA-PU and reflects a rearrangement of the crystallized PBA segments beyond the yield point. Blending the PBA-PU with 10% w/w of PBA led to a significant increase of the Young's modulus (213 MPa) and yield stress (13 MPa), while the elongation at break increased moderately to 400-425% (**Table 2**); interestingly the strain hardening was completely suppressed, perhaps because of the more localized deformations and reduced chain entanglements on account of the increased crystalline content in the blends.⁵⁵ Increasing the

concentration of PBA to 20% and 30% did not lead to significant changes of the tensile behavior *vis-à-vis* the 10% blends.

Table 2. Storage modulus and tensile properties of the neat PBA-PU, and its blends with PBA^a

	E' at 25°C (MPa)	Young's Modulus (MPa)	Yield Stress (MPa)	Maximum Stress (MPa)
PBA-PU	150 ± 50	75 ± 10	6.7 ± 1	23 ± 6.5
10% w/w PBA-PU/ PBA	403 ± 19	213 ± 31	13 ± 1	17.7 ± 2.8
20% w/w PBA-PU/ PBA	411 ± 36	196 ± 0.3	11.7 ± 0.5	12.2 ± 0.6
30% w/w PBA-PU/ PBA	412 ± 35	209 ± 25	11.6 ± 0.6	13.5 ± 0.1

^aAll data represent averages of $N = 3-5$ individual measurements ± standard deviation.

The shape memory behavior of PBA-PU and PBA-PU/PBA blends with 10, 20 or 30 % w/w PBA was investigated on thin films, using a DMA in controlled force mode according to reported protocol.^{27,56} In one set of experiments, the temporary shape was programmed by heating the samples to 70 °C, deforming them to either 40% strain (based on the mechanical characteristics established by tensile testing), and subsequent cooling under applied stress to a given fixing temperature, which was varied with the specific materials crystallization behavior in mind. After maintaining the samples under load at the fixing temperature for typically 5 and in some cases 15, 20 or 30 min, the stress was removed, and the temperature was increased to 70 °C again, to release the temporary shape and (partially) recover the original shape. The cycle was repeated several times. Representative shape memory cycles are shown in **Figures 7, S7-S9** while the values for % fixity and % recovery extracted from all the cycles, using Eqs. 1-2 (see Experimental Section), are reported in **Table 3**. Thermoplastic PUs are known to display an incomplete recovery when they are first deformed (notably at elevated temperatures) due to irrever-

sible hard-segment rearrangements, and therefore cyclic shape memory experiments display a large “hysteresis” between the first and subsequent cycles. To take this into account, the fixity and recovery ratios are usually separately determined for the first and subsequent cycles.

The neat PBA-PU shows an excellent fixity of 98% when programmed at a fixation temperature of 0 °C (**Figure 7a, Table 3**) indicating efficient PBA crystallization at this temperature as suggested by the DSC analysis. Similar fixity values were observed if the fixation was carried out at 10 °C with extended fixation time of 15 min (**Figure 7b, Table 3**). However, the fixity was reduced to 42-48% when it was attempted to fix the material 37 °C, even at a fixing time of 30 min; at the same time, the recovery rate was only 57-88% (**Figure S9a, Table 3**). The 10% w/w PBA-PU/PBA blend displays a higher crystallization temperature (~20 °C, **Figure 1b**), which permitted fixation at 20 °C and 25 °C (extended fixation time) with superior fixity value of 97% (**Figure S9b-d, Table 3**). Increasing the PBA content (20% w/w) further raises the crystallization temperature (DSC shows an onset at ~ 30 °C and a maximum at 23 °C, **Figure 1b**) and the 20% w/w PBA-PU/PBA blend showed a fixity of 94% at a fixing temperature of 25 °C (**Figure 7c**). Further elevating the fixation temperature to 30 °C yielded an excellent fixity of 98% if the fixation time was increased to 15 min (**Figure 7d**). With possible biomedical applications in mind, the fixation temperature was increased to 37 °C, and fixity values of 80 and 98% were achieved at fixing times of 15 and 30 min, respectively (**Figure 7e-f, Table 3**). Also the 20% w/w PBA-PU/AcPBA blend (**Figure S10a**) and the 20% w/w PBA-PU/PBA solution-cast blend (**Figure S10b**) displayed excellent fixity (97%) in the 1st and 2nd cycle when programmed at 37 °C with a fixation time of 30 min. On account of its higher T_c (29 °C), the 30% w/w PBA-PU/PBA blend displayed a good fixity of 96% at 37 °C even with short fixation

time of 15 min while the fixity increased further to 98% when the fixation time was extended to 20 min (**Figure 7g-h, Table 3**).

The data in **Table 3** show further that the fixity achieved in the first programming cycle is generally comparable to that of subsequent cycles, and that the recovery rate is typically 96% or higher, while the lower recovery rate reflects the intrinsic hysteresis associated with the deformation of pristine PU. The data also show that the time/temperature required for fixing the temporary shape can be conveniently controlled via the composition of the blend.

Figure 7. Shape memory tests (temperature-stress-strain cycles) of PBA-PU (a), (b), 20% w/w PBA-PU/PBA blend (c-f), and 30% w/w PBA-PU/PBA blend (g-h). The fixing temperature was 0 °C (a), 10 °C (b), 25 °C (c), 30 °C (d), 37 °C (e-h). In each cycle, the sample was heated to 70 °C, maintained at 70 °C for 5 min, before the force was increased at a rate of 0.8 N·min⁻¹ until the strain reached ca. 40%. The stress and temperature were maintained for 5 min, before the temperature was dropped to the desired fixing temperature. After the fixing temperature had been reached, the stress was maintained for 5 (a), (c), 15 (b), (d), (e), (g), 20 min (h), or 30 min (f). The applied stress was

then removed and the samples were kept at the fixing temperature for another 5 min. Finally, the samples were heated to 70 °C and this temperature was maintained for 10 min to promote shape recovery.

Table 3. Fixity (%) and recovery (%) ratios of the neat PBA-PU, and its blends with 10, 20 or 30% w/w PBA, 20% w/w AcPBA, or 30% w/w PCL.^a

	Shape Fixing Temperature (°C)	Fixity 1 st cycle (%)	Recovery 1 st cycle (%)	Fixity 2 nd & 3 rd cycle ^e (%)	Recovery 2 nd & 3 rd cycle ^e (%)
PBA-PU	0	98 ± 0.7	85 ± 0.2	98 ± 1.0	98 ± 0.2
	10 ^b	98 ± 0.1	75 ± 4.5	98 ± 0.1	97 ± 0.6
	37 ^c	48 ± 0.5	57 ± 2	42 ± 1	88 ± 0.8
10% w/w PBA-PU/PBA	20	98 ± 0.5	78 ± 1.6	97 ± 0.5	97 ± 1.0
	25	95 ± 0.3	76 ± 0.8	45 ± 0.6	97 ± 1.8
	25 ^b	97 ± 0.6	75 ± 0.2	96 ± 1.6	97 ± 1.2
20% w/w PBA-PU/PBA	25	98 ± 0.9	72 ± 1.9	94 ± 1.5	96 ± 1.0
	30	97 ± 1.8	64 ± 0.3	27 ± 1.4	94 ± 0.9
	30 ^b	98 ± 1.3	67 ± 1.0	98 ± 0.4	96 ± 2.8
	37 ^b	97 ± 0.5	68 ± 1.8	80 ± 1.1	95 ± 0.5
	37 ^c	98 ± 0.2	69 ± 0.6	98 ± 0.2	98 ± 0.5
20% w/w PBA-PU/AcPBA	37 ^c	97 ± 0.1	88 ± 1.6	97 ± 0.1	98 ± 0.6
20% w/w PBA-PU/PBA (SC)	37 ^c	98 ± 0.1	90 ± 0.7	98 ± 0.2	99 ± 0.5
30% w/w PBA-PU/PBA	37 ^b	99 ± 0.1	78 ± 1.1	96 ± 0.3	97 ± 1.0
	37 ^d	99 ± 0.1	77 ± 0.3	98 ± 0.5	97 ± 1.1
30% w/w PBA-PU/PCL	37 ^c	98 ± 0.1	67 ± 0.9	97 ± 0.9	97 ± 1.5

^aAll data represent averages of $N=3$ individual measurements \pm standard deviation. The fixation time was 5 min, unless noted. ^bThe fixation time was 15 min. ^c The fixation time was 30 min. ^dThe fixation time was 20 min. ^eThe % fixity and % recovery values are averages from the 2nd and 3rd cycles.

Thus, blending PBA-PU with PBA indeed affords shape memory materials in which a temporary shape can be programmed at a substantially higher temperature than in the case of the neat PBA-

PU; notably, excellent shape fixity can be achieved at physiological temperature. Eliminating the hysteresis effect⁵⁷⁻⁵⁸ in the first shape memory cycles, recovery ratios extracted from 2nd and 3rd cycles were excellent (95-98%) for the neat PBA-PU and its blends with PBA (**Table 3**).

An alternative shape memory cycle was also used to investigate the behavior when deforming the materials only after first cooling them to the fixing temperature. This protocol is perhaps better suited to characterize the behavior under practically useful conditions where an object or device containing the shape-memory material is (i) heated above the transition temperature (T_m) to soften the material, (ii) is cooled to a temperature low enough as to cause no harm or discomfort when inserted in or around the body, and (iii) is positioned in the deployment position where the material adapts its shape to the surrounding environment (i.e. stress is applied) at the body temperature (i.e. 37 °C). As for the shape memory test described above, the cyclic tests start with the sample being heated to 70 °C and being kept at this temperature for 5 min. The samples were then cooled to 37 °C (rate 5 °C/min) to simulate the deployment of an object or a device, and kept at this temperature for 2 min. The samples were then uniaxially deformed, as described above, and kept under load isothermally for 15 min. After the removal of the stress, the cycle proceeded as for the conventional cycle. Gratifyingly, the shape-memory cycle recorded under these conditions for the 20% w/w PBA-PU/PBA blend (**Figure 8**) reveals excellent fixity and recovery of 98 and 97 %, respectively. Moreover, due to the deformation occurring at lower temperature, the hysteresis observed during the first cycle on the standard shape-memory tests is much less pronounced.

Figure 8: Shape memory behavior of the 20% w/w PB-PU/PBA mixture determined in an alternative shape programming and release cycle for. The cycle started with a temperature increase to 70 °C and the sample was maintained at 70°C for 5 min. The sample was then cooled to 37 °C, kept at this temperature for 2min, and deformed by applying a force (rate=0.8 N·min⁻¹), until the strain reached ca. 60%. The stress was maintained for 15 min, removed and the sample was kept at 37°C for another 5 min. Finally, the samples were heated to 70 °C and this temperature was maintained for 10 min to promote shape recovery. The calculated shape fixity and recovery are 98 and 97%, respectively.

To demonstrate the difference between the neat PBA-PU and the 30% w/w PBA-PU blend, with respect to the feasibility of shape-fixation at physiological temperature, star-shaped samples (**Figure 9a**) were heated above the softening temperature of the materials (70 °C) in a water bath (**Figure 9b**) and subsequently shaped in another water bath maintained at 37 °C for 20 min to adapt a temporary shape (**Figure 9c**). The experiment confirmed that such fixing is clearly possible in the case of the 30% w/w PBA-PU/PBA blend, but not the neat PBA-PU (**Figure 9d**).

Finally, we also explored the shape-memory characteristics of the 30% w/w PBA-PU/PCL blend. As expected on the basis of the thermal data, the material shows an excellent fixity of 98% (1st cycle) and 97% (2nd cycle) when programmed for 30 min at a fixation temperature of 37°C (**Figure S11, Table 3**) indicating efficient PBA crystallization at this temperature.

Figure 9: Pictures demonstrating shape fixation at physiological temperature for the neat PBA-PU (left side in each picture) and 30% w/w PBA-PU/PBA blend (right side). (a) Original shape of the samples at room temperature. (b) Samples heated to 70 °C in a water bath. (c) Temporary shape programming by immersing the samples in a water bath maintained at 37 °C for 20 min. (d) Fixed shape of the samples at room temperature.

Conclusions

The thermal, mechanical and shape memory properties of a commercially available shape memory poly(urethane) featuring poly(1,4-butylene adipate) as a crystallizable segment can be tailored by blending this material with commercially accessible, crystalline polyesters. Most interestingly, incorporating free PBA into PBA-PU increased the shape fixing temperature from 10 to 37 °C, which could be very beneficial for the utilization of such material in biomedical applications. The incorporation of free PCL also shifted the crystallization temperature and thus the shape fixation of PBA-PU close to physiological temperature. Simple melt-mixing process was utilized to formulate the blends, which affords an easy route for the property modification of existing SMPs and upscaling of such materials for the technological applications. The nature of the end groups and the processing conditions dictate if there is any reaction between the components, or if the product is merely a blend. If the polyesters employed feature reactive

hydroxyl end groups, transesterification and/or attack of the urea groups occurs under melt-mixing conditions, but such reactions can be effectively suppressed by end capping the polyester that is added. Interestingly, in either case, the addition of PBA or PCL causes nucleation and leads to a significant increase of the crystallization temperature of the switching phase from below to above ambient temperature. The new materials platform is well suited for applications in which a shape is to be fixed at physiological temperature.

Supporting Information

Additional TGA traces of PBA-PU and blends with PBA, DSC data for the neat PBA and additional PBA-PU/PBA blends, SAXS and WAXS spectra of the neat PBA, PCL, PBA-PU, and their blends, NMR, IR, and SEC data for PBA and AcPBA, SEC data for PBA-PU/PCL blends, shape memory cycles of additional PBA-PU/PBA and PBA-PU/PCL blends.

Notes

The employer of the authors has filed a patent application to protect the findings reported herein.

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